

**JESUS' FAMILY AND THE DISCIPLES
NEAR THE CROSS**
**A Redaction-Critical Study of John 19:25-27
in Light of Its Synoptic Parallel**

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Abstract: One of the artworks recurrent in Christian churches is the depiction of the scene at the foot of the Cross. Notably, this art seems to follow the Gospel of John more closely, which describes women as standing near Jesus' cross (Jn 19:25), in contrast to the Synoptic Gospels, where women are portrayed as looking from a distance (Mt 27:55; Mk 15:40; Lk 23:49). Although this scene has been a subject of scholarly discussion, limited attention has been given to the spatial positioning of the individuals depicted, their number, and their identities in relation to the Synoptic accounts. This study therefore seeks to address these aspects and to explore whether there exists a distinctive Johannine motif.

Keywords: Crucifixion of Jesus, Jesus' Family, John 19:25-27, Jesus' Disciples, Women in the Gospel of John.

INTRODUCTION

In the Johannine account of the Crucifixion, several women are portrayed "standing near the cross of Jesus" (19:25). Subsequently, the Gospel introduces a unique scene in which Jesus addresses both his mother and the beloved disciple

with the words, “Woman, here is your son,” ... “Here is your mother” (vv. 26-27).¹ This text has been the focus of extended attention, analysis, and interpretation in New Testament exegesis. John’s account emphasizes the location of the group and their identities in v. 25, and Jesus’ words to his mother and the beloved disciple in vv. 26-27. This study examines the spatial positioning, number, and identities of the individuals present at the foot of the cross in Jn 19:25-27, in comparison with its Synoptic parallels, with a particular attention to the Johannine motif contouring this scene.

1. A COMPARISON OF THE SCENE AT THE FOOT OF CROSS IN THE GOSPELS

The following chart illustrates the scene at the foot of the cross as depicted by the four evangelists. It highlights both similarities and differences in the spatial positioning of the individuals present (indicated in bold), as well as in their number and identities (indicated in underlined italics).

Mk 15:40-41	Mt 27:55-56	Lk 23:49	Jn 19:25-27
<p>⁴⁰ There were also women looking on from a distance; among them were <u>Mary Magdalene, and Mary the mother of James the younger and of Joses, and Salome.</u></p>	<p>⁵⁵ Many women were also there, looking on from a distance; they had followed Jesus from Galilee and had provided for him.</p>	<p>⁴⁹ But all his acquaintances, including the women who had followed him from Galilee, stood at a distance, watching these things.</p>	<p>²⁵ And that is what the soldiers did. Meanwhile, standing near the cross of Jesus were <u>his mother, and his mother’s sister, Mary the wife of Clopas and Mary Magdalene.</u></p>

¹ The biblical quotations are taken from *The Holy Bible Containing the Old and New Testaments with the Apocryphal/Deutero-Canonical Books, New Revised Standard Version* (New York – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1989).

<p>⁴¹ These used to follow him and provided for him when he was in Galilee; and there were many other women who had come up with him to Jerusalem.</p>	<p>⁵⁶ Among them were <u>Mary Magdalene, and Mary the mother of James and Joseph, and the mother of the sons of Zebedee.</u></p>	<p>See Lk 8:2-3 ² as well as some women who had been cured of evil spirits and infirmities: <u>Mary, called Magdalene, from whom seven demons had gone out, ³and Joanna, the wife of Herod's steward Chuza, and Susanna,</u> and many others, who provided for them out of their resources.</p>	<p>²⁶ When Jesus saw his mother and <u>the disciple whom he loved</u> standing beside her, he said to his mother, 'Woman, here is your son.'²⁷ Then he said to the disciple, 'Here is your mother.' And from that hour the disciple took her into his own home.</p>
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2. THE SPATIAL POSITIONING OF THE INDIVIDUALS AT THE CROSS

Regarding the location of those who stood at the cross, the Johannine expression is *near/para* (Jn 19:25), while the Synoptic expression is at a distance / *apo makrothen* (Mt 27:55; Mk 15:40; Lk 23:49). For Rudolf Schnackenburg, "the shaping hand of the Evangelist is recognizable: those looking 'from afar' have become those 'standing near' not only in a local sense but also, in the words to Mary and the disciple, in a figurative sense."² He further observes that, "the whole scene cannot have been added later, say, by editors,

² Rudolf Schnackenburg, *The Gospel According to John*, vol. 3, HThKNT 4/3 (New York: Crossroad, 1987), 275. Schnackenburg identifies Jesus' mother as "Mary," however, the Gospel of John does not explicitly provide her name.

but it is planned by the Evangelist.”³ George Beasley-Murray, suggests that the difference between the Synoptic and Johannine accounts concerning the physical distance of those who stood at the cross is not problematic, since it was natural for the closest relatives (Jesus’ mother and mother’s sister) of the one crucified to reach near the cross.⁴ Ben Witherington concurs that in the given historical situation, it is not surprising that the grieving women, especially the relatives were allowed to be present near the cross.⁵ While Beasley-Murray and Witherington discuss the possibility that Jesus’ closest relatives were permitted to stand near the cross, they do not comment pointedly at the presence of Mary Magdalene and the beloved disciple representing Jesus’ disciples and followers. Similarly, Craig S. Keener claims that even though the bystanders of the cross could not be so close to the cross, they could stand within hearing range.⁶ Interestingly, Reimund Bieringer and Isabelle Vanden Hove focus on the Johannine emphasis of the “closeness to the cross” as a defining characteristic of the new relationship among the members. For John, this closeness is of central significance.⁷ However, they do not specify the essential features of the new relationship that John wants to present in this scene.

M. Sabbe who examines this scene in John and the Synoptics argues that some words in the Johannine narrative

³ Schnackenburg, *The Gospel According to John*, 275. See also C. K. Barrett, *The Gospel According to St. John: An Introduction with Commentary and Notes on the Greek Text* (London: SPCK, 1960), 459; Craig S. Keener, *The Gospel of John: A Commentary*, vol. 2 (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 2003), 1141.

⁴ George Beasley-Murray, *John*, WBC 36 (Waco, TX: Word Books, 1987), 349.

⁵ Ben Witherington, *John’s Wisdom: A Commentary on the Fourth Gospel* (Cambridge: Lutterworth, 1995), 309.

⁶ Keener, *The Gospel of John*, vol. 2, 1141.

⁷ Reimund Bieringer and Isabelle Vanden Hove, “Mary Magdalene in the Four Gospels,” *Louvain Studies* 32/3 (2007): 235. In his later study on Mary Magdalene, “*Mary Magdalene in the Gospel of John*,” in *The Oxford Handbook of Mary Magdalene*, ed., Diane Apostolos-Cappadona (22 May 2024), 1-15, Reimund Bieringer contends that Mary Magdalene exemplifies the role of a “faithful disciple” of Jesus, both at the crucifixion (Jn 19:25) and within the resurrection narrative (Jn 20:1-18).

differ depending on the narrative intent and additionally, the Synoptic accounts do not contradict the Johannine account either.⁸ According to Sabbe, in the Johannine scene of the crucifixion, the verb *heistēkeisan* is used with the preposition *para* + dative *tō staurō* referring to the nearness to Jesus rather than to the cross.⁹ *Para* + dative points to the relationship with the person on the cross and not its spatial meaning. If the evangelist intended to elaborate a dialogue of Jesus with his mother and the beloved disciple, it was natural to change their position from *apo makrothen* of Matthew, Mark, and Luke to *heistēkeisan para* to bring them close to the cross.¹⁰ In Sabbe's view, the Synoptic and Johannine accounts are not so different from one another. The Johannine account can be credible only if those who stood at the cross were at a hearing distance. Sabbe's view is implicitly contradictory; in fact, the Johannine phrase "standing near the cross of Jesus" could be a deliberate Johannine redaction, emphasizing both the physical closeness of the members and their role as witnesses to a significant moment. John's decision to present a group of people directly under the cross has an even greater emphasis, namely that those present were witnesses to what was taking place. The Johannine redaction of the positioning of those who are present at the cross is intentional and serves to advance the theological motif of the Gospel.

3. THE NUMBER OF INDIVIDUALS AT THE CROSS

The major grammatical issue in Jn 19:25-27 revolves around the number and identities of the individuals at the foot of the cross. A few hypotheses have been proposed to account for the number of women at the foot of the cross,¹¹ e.g., the

⁸ M. Sabbe, "The Johannine Account of the Death of Jesus and Its Synoptic Parallels (Jn 19,16b-42)," *ETL* 70/1 (1994): 37. See also, John Henry Bernard, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Gospel according to St. John*, ICC (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1964), 633-634 who argues that "the independent witnesses may honestly and truthfully give different, although not inconsistent, reports of the same events."

⁹ Sabbe, "The Johannine Account of the Death of Jesus," 37.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ Bieringer and Vanden Hove, "Mary Magdalene in the Four Gospels," 235.

two, three, or four-women hypotheses. In what follows, we shall examine them.

3.1 Numbers between the Lines

Scholars such as Esther A. de Boer, Frederick F. Bruce, and Veronica Koperski have argued for the plausibility of a two-women hypothesis.¹² Bruce and Koperski do not provide any grammatical argument to support their claim. Meanwhile, de Boer, who seems to be the most relentless proponent of the two-women hypothesis, posits that only two women can be clearly identified at the foot of the cross, namely Jesus' mother (called Mary of Clopas) and Mary Magdalene.¹³ Although, de Boer does not explain this possibility grammatically, it seems that she thinks that the text presents two groups of women each of which is connected with the conjunction *and/kai* (his mother, and his mother's sister) and who are further described by name in a two-member apposition (Mary the wife of Clopas and Mary Magdalene). Furthermore, the evangelist does not mention the presence of a male disciple in v. 25. Hence, according to her, the beloved disciple in v. 26 cannot be a man. De Boer wonders why the women beside the mother of Jesus (if there are two or three in addition to her) have no part to play in vv. 26-27. While de Boer's viewpoint on this cannot be proved wrong, it is important to note that the Johannine narratives do not always reflect the idea that each listed character has a consequential role. For instance, the narrator lists Jesus and seven disciples in Jn 21:2. However, in the ensuing narrative, only Simon

¹² See also Esther A. de Boer, *The Gospel of Mary: Beyond a Gnostic and a Biblical Mary Magdalene*, JSNTSup 260 (London: T&T Clark, 2004), 160-168; Frederick F. Bruce, *The Gospel of John: Introduction, Exposition and Notes* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1984), 371; Veronica Koperski, "The Mother of Jesus and Mary Magdalene: Looking Back and Forward from the Foot of the Cross in John 19, 25-27," in *The Death of Jesus in the Fourth Gospel*, ed. Gilbert Van Belle, 849-858, BETL 200 (Leuven-Paris-Dudley, MA: Leuven University Press – Peeters, 2007), 856.

¹³ See also de Boer, *The Gospel of Mary*, 160-168.

Peter and the beloved disciple, who was not mentioned in the list of seven, have any role to play.

De Boer contends that the lexeme *son/huios* in v. 26 is a gender-inclusive term and could refer to a female disciple (Mary Magdalene) rather than strictly a male disciple. She cites Jn 12:36 as one instance in which *huioi* does not specify a particular gender, and based on this, she argues that it must be to Mary Magdalene that Jesus entrusts his mother and that they will act as a mother and son. One can nitpick that her argument is inconsistent as she claims that *huios* in 19:26 is a gender-inclusive term, and yet believes that Jesus asks his mother and his beloved disciple to act as mother and son (cf. Jn 19:26).¹⁴ If the lexeme *huios* in v. 26 can be interpreted as a gender-inclusive term, then de Boer should not have translated the term as “son” but rather as “descendant” or “offspring” (in order to express the gender neutrality of the term). In addition to this, she would also need to argue that the beloved disciple is not always the same person in the Gospel of John. For example, in Jn 20:2, Mary Magdalene is reported to have run from the tomb to inform Simon Peter and the beloved disciple that Jesus’ body was missing from the tomb.¹⁵ While there is a distinction in the way the beloved disciple is described (Jn 19:26 uses *agapaō* and 20:2 *phileō*), de Boer would need to make it clear to the reader whether she considers this distinction as a reason why the beloved disciple is a different person in 19:26 and in 20:2-10. More significantly, de Boer’s claim that Jesus’ mother is Mary of Clopas addresses the question of how Clopas might be

¹⁴ Cf. de Boer, *The Gospel of Mary*, 160-168.

¹⁵ In Jn 20:2 Mary Magdalene informs the beloved disciple about the empty tomb. Hence, the argument that Mary Magdalene is the beloved disciple is not convincing. According to Ismo Dunderberg, “The Beloved Disciple in John: Ideal Figure in an Early Christian Controversy,” in *Fair Play: Diversity and Conflicts in Early Christianity*, ed. Ismo Dunderberg, Christopher Tuckett, and Kari Syreeni, NovTsup 103 (Leiden: Brill, 2002), 261-267, “it was common to use the language of a love relationship for the disciples of Jesus who acted as substantiating figures in the early Christian community.”

connected to the mother of Jesus. In de Boer's view, Jesus' mother is the daughter of Clopas.¹⁶ However, it is unlikely that Mary of Clopas will still be referred to as Mary of Clopas if it is believed that she is Clopas' daughter because married women are known by their husbands' names.¹⁷ Besides this, Jesus' mother is not referred to in relation to Clopas elsewhere in the Gospel or anywhere else in the New Testament. Therefore, de Boer's two-women hypothesis will need to be further explained, including how likely it is that two sisters can share the same name within the family.

Scholars who support the three-women hypothesis, such as Hans-Joseph Klauck, Judith M. Lieu, and Ernst W. Hengstenberg, hold that the Mary identified as the sister of Jesus' mother is one and the same person as the Mary of Clopas.¹⁸ Among these scholars, only Klauck seems to argue based on the grammatical construction, while Lieu and Hengstenberg favour the three-women hypothesis without providing sufficient argument for their claim. For Klauck, only three women were at the foot of the cross in Jn 19:25: Jesus' mother, his mother's sister (i.e., Mary of Clopas), and Mary Magdalene.¹⁹ As Klauck sees it, the double coordinating conjunction "and"/"kai" functions to link three separate individuals, namely, Jesus' mother, his mother's sister (who is also the Mary of Clopas), and Mary Magdalene.²⁰ While Klauck defends his case using the conjunction *kai*, he does

¹⁶ Cf. de Boer, *The Gospel of Mary*, 160-168.

¹⁷ John J. Gunther, "The Family of Jesus," *Evangelical Quarterly* 46/1 (1974): 29.

¹⁸ See also Hans-Josef Klauck, "Die dreifache Maria: Zur Rezeption von Joh 19,25 in EvPhil 32," in *The Four Gospels*, ed. F. Van Segbroeck et al., vol. 3, 2343-2358, BETL 100C (Leuven: Leuven University Press-Peeters, 1992), 2347; Judith M. Lieu, "The Mother of the Son in the Fourth Gospel," *JBL* 117/1 (1998): 68; Ernst W. Hengstenberg, *Commentary on the Gospel of John*, vol. 2 (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1879), 415.

¹⁹ Klauck, "Die Dreifache Maria, Zur Rezeption von Joh 19,25 in EvPhil 32," 2347.

²⁰ Klauck, "Die Dreifache Maria. Zur Rezeption von Joh 19,25 in EvPhil 32," 2347-2348.

not discuss the grammatical function of his mother's sister, Mary the wife of Clopas.

The main proponents of the four-women hypothesis in Jn 19:25 are John Henry Bernard, Raymond E. Brown, Rudolf Bultmann, and George Beasley-Murray. These scholars identify the four women at the foot of the cross as Jesus' mother, his mother's sister, Mary of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene. Beasley-Murray rejects the two and three-women hypothesis since they imply that both Jesus' mother and her sister bear the same name, Mary, which is highly unlikely.²¹ So, Beasley-Murray holds that there were definitely four women at the foot of the cross; the first two are not named because they were well known to the community, but the latter two are.²² It is clear from his argument that he assumes two groups of women to be present under the cross, namely, a group of family members, i.e., Jesus' mother and his mother's sister, and a group of disciples, i.e., Mary of Clopas and Mary Magdalene. This means that "Mary of Clopas" is not understood as an apposition. Beasley-Murray does not discuss the awkward use of the conjunction *kai* in this enumeration of supposedly four women whereby the first two and the last two women are tied together with *kai*.

3.2 The Grammatical Possibility

In examining the three hypotheses above, the three-women hypothesis seems to be the least problematic grammatically. Though most of the points raised by Klauck, particularly on the function of the coordinating conjunction *kai* in deciphering the number of women at the foot of the cross are agreeable, it is still necessary to identify other grammatical elements crucial in support of the three-women hypothesis for Jn 19:25. Perhaps the most important of these additional

²¹ Beasley-Murray, *John*, 348.

²² Beasley-Murray, *John*, 350.

grammatical elements is the issue of the use of appositions in the verse. For example, the grammatical structure of “his mother’s sister, Mary the wife of Clopas” can also be interpreted by assuming that “Mary the wife of Clopas” is an apposition to “his mother’s sister.” An apposition “is the placement of two words or word groups parallel to each other without any coordinating particle (*te* or *kai*), with the ‘appositive’ defining or modifying the other. In this way, two noun phrases (each with their own head), may together serve as a single constituent.”²³ From the above definition of how a coordinating conjunction (or particle) is unnecessary in linking a word or group of words which parallels another word or group of words that it modifies (i.e., serving as its apposite), it is significant to ask what is logically possible in the context of the scene in Jn 19:25. In the context of Jn 19:25, only three women are clearly connected by the conjunction and/*kai* (as noted by Klauck and others).

Grammatically, owing to the absence of a coordinating conjunction between the designation his mother’s sister and Mary the wife of Clopas, the designation Mary the wife of Clopas, therefore, functions as an apposition to his mother’s sister. Based on this, this study supports the three-women hypothesis, emphasizing both the function of apposition and the fact that the three members of the enumeration are separated by the conjunction “and”/“*kai*”. Moreover within the framework of the three women hypothesis, it is difficult to overlook the fact that Jesus’ mother and her sister appear to share the same name, a detail attested in the Synoptic tradition (cf. Mk 6:3; Mt 1:16, 18, 20; 2:11; 13:55; Lk 1:27, 30; 2:5), even though John does not identify Jesus’ mother as Mary. However, the designation “his mother’s sister” may plausibly refer to a cousin, a possibility that cannot be discounted.

²³ Evert Van Emde Boas et al., *The Cambridge Grammar of Classical Greek: A New Reference Grammar for Classical Greek: Aims and Principles* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019), 319.

Our grammatical analysis of Jn 19:25 supports the three-women hypothesis in which the three women at the foot of the cross are identified as Jesus' mother, his mother's sister, who is Mary, the wife of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene. Notably, the beloved disciple is not included in the initial enumeration of the women, but attention shifts to him in the subsequent verses. Accordingly, the Johannine account of the crucifixion portrays a scene comprising these three women alongside the beloved disciple.

4. THE IDENTITIES OF INDIVIDUALS AT THE FOOT OF THE CROSS

It is noteworthy that all four evangelists agree on the presence of women at the crucifixion. In the preceding section, the three women hypothesis was proposed as the most plausible explanation regarding those present at the cross, namely Jesus' mother; his mother's sister, Mary the wife of Clopas; and Mary Magdalene. The present section, therefore, focuses on analyzing the identities of these women, comparing them with the Synoptic accounts.

A key distinction between John and the Synoptics lies in the placement of the women's attendance in the narrative: the Synoptic Gospels focus on the women's presence following Jesus' death, whereas John situates them at the scene before Jesus' death. Mark lists three women: Mary Magdalene, Mary the mother of James the younger and Joses, and Salome (Mk 15:40). Mark presents the first two Marys: Mary Magdalene and Mary, the mother of James and Joses at the burial (Mk 15:47, no mention of James here) and the empty tomb. However, in the resurrection narrative, Mark presents the three women again who were mentioned at the cross (Mk 16:1, no mention of Joses here). Matthew's account of women closely follows Mark's list of women. Matthew lists three women at the crucifixion: Mary Magdalene, Mary the mother of James and Joseph, and the mother of the sons of Zebedee (Mt 27:55-56). However, Mark's "Mary, the mother of James the younger and Joses,"

is redacted by Matthew to Mary the mother of James and Joseph avoiding the use of “younger” and replacing “Joses” with “Joseph.” It is possible that Matthew’s “mother of the sons of Zebedee” and Mark’s “Salome” refer to the same person. Matthew may have chosen to identify her in this way because he had already introduced her earlier in 20:20, where she approaches Jesus with a request that her two sons be granted places at his right and left in his kingdom. Further, Matthew refers to two of the women, identifying them as “Mary Magdalene and the other Mary,” in both the burial and resurrection narratives (Mt 27:61; 28:1).

Luke does not specify the women at the crucifixion.²⁴ For him, it suffices to convey that the women followed Jesus from Galilee to the burial. Thus, he refrains from repeating their names but mentions them collectively as women at the crucifixion scene. The list of women in Lk 8:2-3 begins with Mary Magdalene, whom Luke identifies as the woman from whom seven evils spirits had gone out. After Mary Magdalene, Luke mentions Joanna, the wife of Herod’s steward Chuza, and Susanna (they are not mentioned in other Gospels) along with “many others” who provided for Jesus and his disciples²⁵ from their own resources.²⁶ However, when Luke names the women at the tomb (Lk 24:10), he includes not only Mary Magdalene and Joanna, previously introduced in 8:2, but also Mary the mother of James, who appears in the accounts of Mark and Matthew.

Mark and Matthew both emphasize the verbs “to provide/care” (*diakoneō*) and “to follow” (*akoloutheō*), specifically noting that the women had followed Jesus “from Galilee” and provided for him (Mk 15:40; Mt 27:55). Luke uses only the verb *diakoneō* (8:3) to indicate that these women

²⁴ According to Bieringer and Vanden Hove, “Mary Magdalene in the Four Gospels,” 213, “Luke introduces the women at the chronological moment when they start playing a role in Jesus’ ministry, so that the readers will remember them as the story unfolds.”

²⁵ This translation is based on the use of αὐτοῖς in the dative plural which is the text-critical decision of NA²⁸.

²⁶ Bieringer and Vanden Hove, “Mary Magdalene in the Four Gospels,” 214-217, provides a detailed discussion on this.

provided for Jesus and his disciples out of their resources, though the Synoptic Gospels do not specify what exactly they provided.²⁷ John does not use either of these terms in reference to the women. Notably, the mentioning of the women in the Synoptics is open ended as indicated by: there were women (Mk 15:40), many women (Mt 27:55), some of the women (Lk 8:2), and many others (Lk 8:3), which suggests the presence of additional women beyond those explicitly listed. John lists the women as his mother and his mother's sister, Mary the wife of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene. Mary Magdalene is the only woman who is listed both in John and in the Synoptics. Mary the wife of Clopas is an apposition to his mother's sister, so that at the cross there were three women: Jesus' mother; his mother's sister, Mary, the wife of Clopas; and Mary Magdalene.²⁸ Mary the wife of Clopas then would be Jesus' aunt. Some scholars associate Mary the wife of Clopas with Mary, mother of James and Joses/Joseph in the Synoptic accounts (cf. Mk 15:40; Mt 27:55),²⁹ an identification that may be possible. The inclusion of Jesus' mother and Mary, wife of Clopas, at the crucifixion scene is unique to the Gospel of John, and notably, they are not mentioned at the discovery of the open tomb, only Mary Magdalene is present there (Jn 20:1).

An interesting feature of John's Gospel is that Mary Magdalene is introduced for the first time at the crucifixion, with no reference to her presence during Jesus' ministry.³⁰

²⁷ François Bovon, *Das Evangelium nach Lukas*, Evangelisch-kritischer Kommentar 1 (Zürich: Benziger Verlag, 1989), 400, opines that "these women are responsible for the provisions of the community of Jesus, and they finance their shopping out of their own property."

²⁸ See also, Bauckham, *Gospel Women*, 204-212 who discusses the possibility that Mary of Clopas was Jesus' cousin.

²⁹ Beasley-Murray, *John*, 348. See also, J. N. Sanders and B. A. Mastin, *A Commentary on the Gospel According to St John: Black's New Testament Commentaries* (London: Black, 1968), 407; D. A. Carson, *The Gospel According to John* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, Leicester, and Inter-Varsity, 1991), 616.

³⁰ In Mark and Matthew also, she is first mentioned at the crucifixion, with the added detail that she had been following Jesus from Galilee, suggesting her

She is also listed alongside members of Jesus' family and appears last in the sequence of women, whereas, in the Synoptic Gospels she is first in the lists of women. The variations in John, particularly in the naming of the women such as the reference to Jesus' mother, the way certain figures are identified such as Jesus' mother's sister Mary, wife of Clopas, and the change in the order of their listing such as Mary Magdalene last in the list, suggest possible Johannine redaction. The discussion above indicates that Mary Magdalene is consistently mentioned across all four Gospels. If one assumes that Mark's Mary, mother of James and Joses, Matthew's Mary, mother of James and Joseph, and John's reference to Jesus' mother's sister, Mary wife of Clopas, refer to the same individual, and that Mark's Salome and Matthew's mother of the sons of Zebedee are identical, it follows that certain figures mentioned in John and Luke, such as Jesus' mother in John and Joanna and Susanna in Luke, have no direct parallels in the other Gospels.

Mk 15:40: Mary Magdalene / Mary mother James and Joses / Salome

M 27:56: Mary Magdalene / Mary mother of James and Joseph / Mother of the sons of Zebedee

Lk 8:2-3: Mary Magdalene / Joanna, the wife of Herod's steward Chuza / Susanna

Jn 19:25: Jesus' mother / Mother's sister, Mary wife of Clopas / Mary Magdalene

John distinctively includes the mother of Jesus among the group of women and places her in the first position. More significant is the address of the Johannine Jesus to her with the term "Woman"/*gynai* (2:3; 19:26). In the New Testament, Jesus addresses five women using this term excluding the woman caught in adultery (7:53–8:11),³¹ the

presence throughout his ministry. However, Luke introduces her earlier, in chapter 8:2, as one of the women who accompanied Jesus.

³¹ This is a text-critically uncertain passage. For a detailed discussion, see, Jennifer Knust, "Early Christian Re-writing and the History of the Pericope

Canaanite woman (Mt 15:28), the woman afflicted with spirit of infirmity (Lk 13:12), Jesus' mother (Jn 2:4; 19:26), the Samaritan woman (Jn 4:21), and Mary Magdalene (20:15). However, Jesus' use of woman/*gynai* in addressing his mother in Jn 2:4 and 19:26 cannot be equated with his address to other women whom he did not know.³² Jesus' use of *gynai* when addressing his mother carries a unique significance distinct from his address to other women in the Gospel. The evangelist's emphasis on her as Jesus' mother and his mother, and Jesus' own use of *gynai* for his mother, reflects a distinction. At the wedding at Cana in Jn 2:1-11, the narrator emphasizes the motherhood between Jesus and his mother four times, while Jesus' own address as *gynai* highlights her broader role in standing for the need of the Cana couple. Under the cross, the narrator emphasizes again her being the mother of Jesus three times while Jesus addresses her as *gynai* extending her motherhood to the beloved disciple. The evangelist highlights her motherhood to emphasize her relationship with Jesus, while Jesus' own use of *gynai* to address her reflects her broader role as a woman. In addressing her as *gynai*, Jesus expands her role beyond biological motherhood, entrusting her to the beloved disciple and thus extending her maternal role. This is further illustrated in Jn 19:26-27, where Jesus says "Woman, here is your son" ... "Here is your mother."

The presence of the beloved disciple is not referred to in the listing of those standing near the cross in v. 25 but

Adulterae," *JECS* 14 (2006): 485-536.

³²There are five main theories in recent scholarship regarding Jesus' address to his mother as γυναίκα. I characterize these theories as: (1) Distancing Theory, see, Hartwig Thyen, *Das Johannesevangelium*, Auflage 2, HNT 6 (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2015), 153. (2) Contextual Theory, see, Judith M. Lieu, "The Mother of The Son in the Fourth Gospel," *JBL* 117/1 (1998): 65. (3) Relativising Theory, see, Aleksandra Nalewaj, "Matka Jezusa" i „Niewiasta" jako tytuły Maryi w czwartej Ewangelii," *RBL* 63/1 (2010): 28. (4) Transitioning Theory, see, Kenneth Mtata, "Gender and Metaphor of Childbirth in the Gospel of John," *New Testament Society of Southern Africa Conference* (2013): 11-12. (5) Symbolizing Theory, see, Raymond E. Brown, *The Gospel According to John (I-XII): Introduction, Translation, and Notes*, AB 29 (Garden City, NY: Doubleday, 1966), 109.

is introduced in the following vv. 26-27. The expression the “disciple whom Jesus loved” (Jn 19:26), as well as the presence of a male disciple³³ at the crucifixion, is notably absent from the Synoptic Gospels. According to John Henry Bernard, the beloved disciple is the author of the Fourth Gospel who has recorded the crucifixion account, suggesting that this may be the reason why he is mentioned only in John and not the Synoptics.³⁴ The beloved disciple must have remembered the crucifixion account since it is to him that Jesus addressed these words from the cross.³⁵ He argues that “the independent witnesses may honestly and truthfully give different, although not inconsistent, reports of the same events.”³⁶ However, Bernard does not discuss why Jesus entrusts his mother to the beloved disciple before his death or what kind of relationship is being established between Jesus’ mother and the beloved disciple. The reference to “disciple whom Jesus loved” at the foot of the cross along with Jesus’ words to him “here is your mother” (19:26), are unique to the Gospel of John. The four occurrences of “the disciple whom he loved” (13:23; 19:26; 21:7; 21:20) spotlight his particular significance within the Johannine passion narrative.

5. THE THEOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE SCENE AT THE FOOT OF THE CROSS IN JOHN 19:25-27

In the Johannine account, the ordering of the women at the cross seems to be deliberate. John measuredly places the mother of Jesus first in the list. She is followed by her sister Mary, the wife of Clopas, who also belongs to the biological

³³ de Boer, *The Gospel of Mary*, 160-168, argues that the absence of a male disciple in v. 25 means the beloved disciple in v. 26 cannot be a man, rather, it must be Mary Magdalene who is referred to in Jn 19:26.

³⁴ Bernard, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Gospel According to St. John*, 633-634.

³⁵ *Ibid.*, 633-634.

³⁶ *Ibid.*, 34.

family of Jesus. Last in the sequence stands Mary Magdalene, who represents the wider circle of women who followed Jesus. After mentioning the presence of the women, the narrative focus shifts directly to the mother of Jesus and to the beloved disciple whom Jesus addresses from the cross saying “Woman, here, is your son” ... “Here is your mother” (Jn 19:26-27). According to Bieringer, Mary Magdalene exemplifies the role of a “faithful disciple” of Jesus both at the cross and in the resurrection narrative.³⁷ In Jn 19:25, the sister of Jesus’ mother, Mary, the wife of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene are implicitly presented as witnesses to the crucifixion. The narrative centers on Jesus’ entrustment of his mother and the beloved disciple to one another in a mother-son relationship. This new mother-son relationship is not merely symbolic but carries a literal dimension, underscored in 19:27 by the statement that the beloved disciple took her “into his own” / *eis ta idia*. If the evangelist’s intention had been solely to highlight Jesus’ mother and the beloved disciple, the mention of the other women would have been unnecessary. Their inclusion suggests that the emphasis extends beyond individuals to two representative groups: Jesus’ mother embodies his biological family, while the beloved disciple represents the community of disciples. These two groups are joined in a new familial relationship at the foot of the cross. This scene, found only in the Gospel of John, is distinctive to Johannine theology of “Family” at the climactic moment of Jesus’ crucifixion.

CONCLUSION

In the crucifixion scene, the Gospel of John portrays the women as “standing near the cross of Jesus” and the words of Jesus to his mother and to the beloved disciple, “Woman, here is your son” ... “Here is your mother,”

³⁷ Bieringer, “Mary Magdalene in the Gospel of John,” 1-15.

hold distinctive significance within the passion narrative. This study has focused primarily on the Johannine spatial positioning of the individuals at the cross, as well as their number and identities, in comparison with the Synoptic accounts. The Johannine phrase “standing ‘near’ the cross of Jesus” in comparison to the Synoptic expression “at a distance” could be a deliberate Johannine spatial redaction, indicative of both the physical closeness of the members and their role as witnesses to a significant relational moment. John presents three women, namely, Jesus’ mother, his mother’s sister, Mary wife of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene and in subsequent verses the beloved disciple. The first two members represent Jesus’ biological family while Mary Magdalene and the beloved disciple represent Jesus’ disciples/followers. John mentions the presence of Jesus’ mother’s sister, identified as Mary wife of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene as standing close to the cross of Jesus and implicitly bearing witness to Jesus’ words to his mother and the beloved disciple. This scene highlights the Johannine theology of “Family,” in which Jesus’ mother is entrusted to the beloved disciple, and the beloved disciple is, in turn, entrusted to her, thereby establishing a new familial relationship that has no direct parallel in the Synoptic Gospels.